

Supplementary material 2.

Codebook

Own elaboration. Source. Exported file of the focus groups and interviews content analysis, through MAXQDA Pro (v. 20.2.2).

Theme 1. Assessment of the tool. This theme coded the segments that referred to distinctive features of VR such as the immersion and realism of the learning environment, and the usefulness attributed to the Didacalia VC system to promote classroom management competence in initial teacher training.

Categories	Definition	Examples of coded quotations
1.1. Immersion	The user perceives that he/she is inside a 3D environment in which he/she can interact with students as if he/she was teaching in a classroom.	<p>It's very nice, the virtual glasses and all that, it feels like you're in a classroom, it does feel like it. And I didn't get dizzy or anything. It was great and you could move around freely. It was like a school. [E_6_00:00:50]</p> <p>The immersive virtual reality experience, being the first time, I find it a bit shocking. That is, once you put on the glasses, you get immersed in a somewhat strange reality. It is true that it was obviously noticeable that we were not in something very realistic, the graphics were somewhat, well, normal, you could tell it was an educated classroom and well, I still found it very interesting. It seemed to me, for example, that the facial expressions of the avatars were very appropriate to the situations that would happen. And it was very interesting because I was able to get into the role and, at the same time, I was able to react naturally enough. It's how I would have reacted during the classes. [GF_7_00:01:12]</p> <p>When I had to face the different conflicts that appeared, I felt very nervous. Since the situations were so unexpected, what happened to me was that I was very nervous when it came to reacting. Very much so, because of course, I was waiting for something to happen because of the kind of activity it involved and that created a lot of nerves and a lot of uncertainty. [GF_5_00:00:19]</p> <p>For us, for example, who are just starting out, it is useful for us to see what we might encounter and to put ourselves in the position of saying "Okay, I'm a teacher, and I have X students in front of me and they're messing me up" [GF_1_00:13:21]</p>
1.2. Realism	The user interacts in the different scenarios that simulate conflict situations and reacts in	What I especially liked is the type of conflict that could arise. I have seen them very realistic and something that could happen perfectly in a high school class, such as a student insulting, saying an insult in the middle of the class, or two students who do not want to separate or sit together. These are situations that are perfectly realistic and that could happen to me next year when I start

	<p>them in a similar way as he would in a real secondary classroom.</p> <p>working as a secondary school teacher. [GF_7_00:02:13]</p> <p>There would have to be some intervention on the part of the students (avatars). Not only at the end that they tell you how you have done it, but while you are doing that the students answer you to show if what you have proposed works. To show that they react positively to what you have proposed, or that they refuse, which can also be the case, but that they talk. [GF_6_00:04:32]</p> <p>Yes, it's certainly true that, for example, I didn't control the Joystick at all in the first one I had technical problems and so it went very badly because I also didn't listen to the student and then I also don't think that a criterion was to approach you. And I didn't control anything. So, I said I didn't know how to approach. In other situations, I would have moved more and so on. [GF_4_00:01:41]</p> <p>I would like to have a test scene (he means that before the first scene there would be a tutorial to get used to the environment (movement, controls...)) [GF_1_00:00:58]</p>
<p>1.3. Usefulness</p> <p>This refers to the ease of use of the tool and the potential attributed to it in terms of its use in learning and teaching the classroom management competence.</p>	<p>I think that for students [of the master's program] it is very good. I think we should all go through it, because the nerves of "I just walked into a class, again, they don't know me," I think it's good. - Yes, I think so too. [GF_1_00:18:06]</p> <p>Yes, it has been a very enriching experience. I had never thought that we could work on conflict issues in the classroom with a tool like this. So, this has been something innovative and I think it has a great potential for our teacher training. [GF_4_00:00:21]</p> <p>It has been very interesting, to be honest, very positive, because sometimes I do think that it is difficult to have this possibility of experimenting in the classroom, in addition to or before the internship. And of course, there is also the fear of internships, it depends on how you respond. Well, of course, they are real students, and it has an impact, on the other hand, here it's good, because being a digital, virtual environment you can practice. And I know that, for example, now, especially the feedback afterwards with colleagues, who have said look, I would have done this differently and so on, and surely if I were to repeat it now, I would improve. And I also think that it would be great for the internship at school because if another similar situation happens to me, then the ones I have been practicing right now, then I will know a little bit more how to respond. [GF_4_00:00:20]</p> <p>Practicing these situations (in VR) helps you to know yourself, how you react (to a conflict) (...) In a video it is easy to criticize. Well, look, I think this teacher is doing badly because ...I would have done something else; but then when it's your turn to act it's a different matter. [GF_4_00:05:43]</p>

I think it is a very nice option. In fact, being a game, we can put it on pause. Obviously, pause to think. Of course, this would be an ideal exercise to do in psychology class. Of you, to be doing this activity and to have, okay, let's stop and discuss it with the whole class. What would you do? What could you do? What would be a possible action-reaction? Let's see, we already do that with videos. But of course, this is a much more interactive way. You expose yourself to the situation. Being the spectator is not the same as being the protagonist. [GF_7_00:29:49]

Yes, and I would like to say one positive thing, unlike videos, where you only observe the fact that it happens, virtual reality allows you to participate and I think that's very good, and if someday we can make this virtual reality better and there could be more interaction, it could be a very powerful tool. [GF_3_00:01:50]

Yes, I think the cool thing about virtual reality is (participation), because in the case of videos, you see the video, and you say, I would never do that, it's super rational, and you think you would never do that, you would do it differently, because you have time to think and give your opinion, but virtual reality allows you, or could allow you, to be inside, and live it, be in that situation and know how you would do it, and what you would say. If it wasn't really a 30-second scene. If it was a class, even if it was about 15 minutes, a longer thing, yes you could get more into the role and feel yourself inside the classroom, and really see how you would react. No, with such a rational thing as watching a video and then doing a reflection. [GF_3_00:02:18]

Theme 2. Evidence of joint construction of knowledge. In this theme we have coded the episodes in which some evidence of joint learning or action that fosters the emergence of such learning is manifested, and which appear in the interviews and in the discussion groups analysed.

Categories	Definition	Examples of coded quotations
2.1. Identifying feared situations	Participants express concern about not knowing how to manage incidents that they may face in the future.	<p>[00:08:05] The second situation was the girl who told you "This is rubbish", which I think is one of the most common that we can find in class.</p> <p>[00:08:21] Or not verbalize it so much but realize that you have half the class asleep.</p> <p>[00:08:26] Wow, I wouldn't know what to do there.</p> <p>[00:08:26] But, I think you've solved it well, you've tried to encourage them. [GF_13, specialization: Catalan language]</p> <p>[00:11:36] I don't know how to solve it either, but you did think when you were doing it, I thought wrong, wrong in the sense that another child who has been behaving well up to now will jump out</p>

<p>2.2. Dilemmas about how to deal with an incident</p>	<p>They reveal doubts and/or confrontations about how to manage disruptive behaviours</p>	<p>and say "I want to change groups too, I don't like my group because she does, and I don't. And I thought, wow, this is conflictive, I don't know how I would solve it, how I would act to avoid this, but I did think it could have a negative effect on our management. And I thought, wow, this is conflictive, I don't know how I would solve it, how I would act to avoid this, but I did think that it could have a negative effect on our management. [GF 13, specialization: Catalan language]</p> <hr/> <p>[00:04:23] So, it's hard. What do you do? Do you leave the class and take it with you? No, because you leave the ruckus in class. [GF_6, Degree specialisation: Modern Languages - French]</p> <p>You've already put the students in some places and then you come in and find them changed. Of course. What do you do? Well, for example, in my case, I said, well guys, put you back where I put you. But of course, they started to make fun of me, and I started to raise my finger. Of course, in this case, I was a little bit like, what do I do? I ignore the attitude and continue so as not to give it too much importance, because, if not, we prolong the conflict. Or if I listen to him and tell him, let's see, don't do that, I don't know what, I don't know how much. [GF_6, Degree specialisation: Modern Languages - French].</p> <p>[00:08:58] What I ask you, I now come out of doubt. The fact that I used a word that technically is a bad sounding word and therefore this is an insult and you're speaking badly. Wouldn't you have referred in conflict resolution? It's about teaching children to speak that register in a classroom, in a classroom you shouldn't talk like that. At home you speak however you want, but not here.</p> <p>[00:09:23] But you would stop the class to give an explanation?</p> <p>[00:09:26] No, not that. I would tell him later. [GF_13, Degree specialisation: Catalan Language & Literature]</p> <p>[00:08:04] I would do... Of course, moving them around would waste time.</p> <p>[00:08:12] Do not move them directly, but tell them each to their place</p> <p>[00:08:15] But they already started to get a little violent, to say "I don't want to".</p> <p>[00:08:21] Because, of course, if you say sit here, sit here, sit here, here, here and they say no, we don't want to.</p> <p>[00:08:29] Yes, there are days and cases like that, when they tell you, I don't change places, I'm fine, I'm comfortable. What do you do? Maybe, at that moment I will think, maybe it doesn't matter, I'll leave it in its place.</p> <p>00:08:43] This depends on how they behave.</p> <p>[00:08:45] But, I would insist, that's it. They were talking, they were interrupting in class all the time. You must change this, yes or yes. [GF_6, Degree specialisation: Modern Languages - French]</p>
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2.3. Re-signifying the experience

Participants evoke previous experiences and re-signify them in the light of the incident they are reflecting on.

[00:04:44] Well, maybe in an isolated case like this, it might be okay to ignore it. I once saw a student in class who had autism and was making spoilers for everything the teacher said. She didn't swear, but she did say impertinent things. And of course, if you paid attention to her all the time, you gave her the limelight. The teacher didn't pay attention to him, they continued their lesson without giving importance to what he had said. If it is something specific, you don't pay attention to it. Of course, but if it is more and more, if she insists more, then it's something else. [GF_10, Degree specialisation: Spanish Language & Literature]

[00:10:14] This is a strategy, like we talked about yesterday, which my teacher also uses it a lot, which is like I tell you, without telling you off, but I tell you, minimizing the impact, but you don't stop the class, because it's like you stop and go on, and I think it's a good strategy. [GF_13, Degree specialisation: Catalan Language & Literature]

[00:06:24] It's just that I'm thinking in the school where I saw they have every class a flow chart of how they're seated so that the teacher coming in could check it out. And then if you work like that, they're not going to fool the English teacher who comes in now and has no idea.

[00:06:43] Yeah, yeah, yeah, yeah, yeah. [GF_10, Degree specialisation: Catalan Language & Literature]

[00:09:30] For example, I saw in a Catalan class that they said a sentence and the teacher said, "You said *ondia*, ¿yes?" It was a bad word in Catalan and the teacher projected it to "*ondia*!" and I liked it because it showed that she had realized that it was a bad word that I am correcting, but in good (manners) and you yourself (the student) tell me yes, because you know that you did it wrong and that this should not be said in the context of the classroom. He did it right, you know, there was no bad feeling, there was nothing. What happened kind of tiptoed by, but he did make reference to "*hostia*" and she said, you said "*hostia*", right? And the boy: yes... (changes his tone, as if embarrassed)

[GF_13, Degree specialisation: Catalan Language & Literature]

[00:07:48] Management is much more difficult this way. For example, we were between 5 and 8 teachers in class and if a [student] is bothering you, you can continue teaching while another teacher....

[00:07:53] Yes, yes, you have more margin...

[00:07:56] Yes, of course, this is very convenient, the teachers make a team, if while you...

[00:08:01] of course, it's not the same as managing a group of 30 people by yourself... when I was in secondary school ...

2.4. Delineating key factors of incident management in the classroom

Participants identify factors and key aspects of the classroom management process whilst reflecting on challenges or possible adverse effects of using a given strategy.

[GF_1, Degree specialisation: Geography and History]

[00:04:44] Well, maybe in an isolated case like this, it might be okay to ignore it. I once saw a student in class who had autism and she was making spoilers for everything the teacher said. She didn't swear, but she did say impertinent things. And of course, if you paid attention to her all the time, you gave her the limelight. The teacher didn't pay attention to him, they continued their lesson without giving importance to what he had said. If it's a one-time thing, you don't give it any importance. Of course, but if it goes further, if she insists more, then it's something else... [GF_2, Degree specialisation: Physics and Chemistry]

[06:19] When there was a problem, stop, think about what to do and then you approached the student. You would ask him if we could fix the problem in some way, why he had gotten that way and try to manage the conflict a little bit, by talking. So, I've seen it right; that's what I would do. I would not shout as we have seen in some cases, because I believe that this way the conflict is fed more, but I would not be impassive either; because, in other words, there are teachers, I have talked to them, who say "what I usually do is to stay still, I just watch them in silence. And when they notice that I am silent, still, they usually stop". Of course, I wouldn't look for that either because at the first time they do it, but then they will say "well, that's where it stays". [GF_1, Degree specialisation: Educational Guidance and Counselling]

[00:04:59] The first time he caught you, as he caught you, who were explaining, first tell him: "Please, Pablo, can you sit down, we are doing some work, I am explaining the instructions and you have to listen well". If he does not agree to sit down, what I would also do would be to finish the explanation (for the whole class) and once finished, making sure that the rest of the students in the class are busy, talk specifically with him, convince him to sit down, ask him what he is feeling, what is happening, why he got up, if it is because he needs to get up for something, and that's it. [GF_6, Degree specialisation: Modern Languages - French]

[00:04:10] This also depends on the students; they are not all the same. Some do not say anything, and you have to act according to the case, in one way or another. [GF_10, Degree specialisation: Spanish Language & Literature]

[00:05:35] For example, the first one, the cooperative groups, it is true that you solve the problem at that moment, but then in the next class you are going to find yourself in the same situation, which is that they want to sit together. And what you can't do is to be every day doing cooperative groups because they want to sit together. So, as a resolution for that moment, yes, in the short term. But in the long term that's not going to help you, because if not, then you're going to have

to be always doing cooperative groups. [GF_13, Degree specialisation: Catalan Language & Literature]

[00:04:45] I think it would be a first step, we have tried to placate the problem, and then, a second action, more personal, I would approach the student and ask him what was going on and something like that.

[00:04:58] Sure. [GF_6, Degree specialisation: Modern Languages - French]

[00:06:53] But it is true, and I agree with what you said, which is that you did not raise the tone of voice, that he (the colleague performing the experience), more or less, was talking like when he was talking during the presentation and, therefore, you do not see a teacher who is angry, who has been particularly stung. Well, he comments on things and that's it. And in fact, to the first character (student avatar), to David, he asked what's the matter with what's the matter with you? It's true that you don't move because you didn't know that you could move with the joystick. But there is a first question, which would be, ask you what happens to the student, and you ask him directly. Well, maybe he (the student-avatar) could have told you that something was wrong, or maybe not, he was just not talking to you and that's all.

[00:07:31] Sure, I probably would have been displaced live, in David's case,

[00:07:36] Sure, and you wouldn't have "missed" him. Maybe if you had come closer, he would have answered you and explained what was wrong with him.

[GF_7, Degree specialisation: Geography and History]

2.5. Questioning the effectiveness of management actions and strategies

Participants propose alternative strategies that are considered to be more effective or complementary to those chosen by the user in virtual reality.

It is also true that I think that in the end, if you approach 90% of the students, if you approach them and talk to them in a low voice and ask them: What happened? What is happening to you? I think that in the end almost all of them will answer you. I guess what this is trying to teach is that if you do it in front of the whole class in a loud voice Hey, what's going on? then it is more difficult for the other person to tell you the truth because he knows that everyone is listening to him. (...)

-Yes, yes, maybe this is a good extraction of reality, isn't it, what we have done in the game? Yes, as usual, leaving the role of being in the school, and approaching that student face to face and asking him what happened.

-Yes, the fact is, yes. [GF_3_ Degree specialisation: Educational Guidance and Counselling, audio clip 41-42]

[00:10:37] Yes, he said, asshole.

[00:10:38] That's right, and how did you react?

[00:10:44] I ignored what they said.

[00:10:46] And how could you have reacted in that situation?

[00:10:49] In a real situation, it's disrespectful. But of course, you think it's like in the background and you don't know who's saying it. You think you're in front of a class of twenty something students.

[00:11:03] Yeah, but in this case, there weren't that many students and you detect who's saying it. what do you do?

[00:11:09] Of course. Then with him (the one who said the swear word) we will have a separate conversation, at the end of the class, always. I'll try not to waste my time.

[00:11:22] But at the beginning of class he's doing it and if you don't stop him, he'll keep doing it, he'll keep doing it, even if you ignore him.

[00:11:29] Yeah, sure, it'll give him a wakeup call, tell him to see what you're doing is not right....

[GF_6, Degree specialisation: Modern Languages - French]

[00:03:57] Yeah, but, for example, in the first case, when Pablo got up. Let's say, let's leave him there, let him do whatever he wants, you don't listen to him. If that happens, would you leave him there, let him do whatever he wants, come on!

[00:03:57] No, I mean sure, I would try to ignore him for a while, until he gets tired. But most likely he's going to keep going.

[00:04:17] But then he'll get attention, that student will get attention and the students will be reinforcing him, you won't be able to follow the class.

[00:04:23] So, it's hard, what do you do, do you walk out of the class and take it away? No, because you leave the ruckus in class.

[00:04:33] It would be to go and approach him and talk to him.

[00:04:37] There, inside the classroom?

[00:04:38] Yes, there inside the classroom and tell him please, sit down and then we'll talk more about it, you know?

[00:04:45] I think that would be a first management, we tried to placate the problem and then a second question, more personal, I approach the student and ask him what was going on and something like that.

[00:04:58] Sure.

[GF_6_ Degree specialisation: Modern Languages - French]

[00:11:09] Of course. Then with him (the one who said the swear word) we will have a separate conversation, at the end of class, always. I'll try not to waste my time.

[00:11:22] But at the beginning of class he's doing it and if you don't stop him he'll keep doing it, he'll keep doing it, even if you ignore him.

[00:11:29] Yeah, sure, I'll give him a wakeup call, tell him to see what you're doing is not right....

[00:11:38] And if he decides to continue, because that's probably what he's going to do.

[00:11:41] He's making it difficult for me.

[00:11:43] No, it's because it's reality.

[00:11:44] Of course, if he continues, I would have to, if we took it to another level, I would call the management, I don't know, I will make a report or whatever, because he doesn't stop and he's not respecting me. Well, first I will try to mediate a little bit, okay, why is he saying this?

[GF_6, Degree specialisation: Modern Languages - French]

[00:12:06] Yeah, but I think what she's missing is that I don't know the students, you know?

[00:12:15] Yeah, but when you're a substitute you're not going to have a clue either.

[00:12:15] Yeah, but maybe that happens to me the first week, but then I know who gets along with who, who doesn't have a good relationship, who to put Maria with to calm her down. I don't know, I don't have a context, there are only 8 or 9 people and I don't know how to manage them because I don't know if Antonio gets along with Maria.

[00:12:37] Yeah, but in the case that you didn't know them, maybe instead of doing the good thing directly, we change the group, the first option would have been "you watch... give him another type of charge that maybe is a little bit more... What happens is that it is true that maybe they can cause everyone to react the same way.

[00:12:53] Of course, also if you are a substitute teacher, and you go the first time, I think you can see the classroom climate between them, even if you don't know them. You can see the alliances that they have as soon as you enter (...)

[00:13:28] Maybe the solution at the beginning is to tell them to do another type of task or to change the group, and if you see that the reaction that this produces another type of reaction, for example, the same reaction of other students, that there are more than one that says Ah, well me too, then you can change the dynamic and say instead of doing it in groups, let's do it this way. You will have this position, you will have this one, you will have this one, you will have this one, you will have this one and you will work individually and then go to the group.

[GF_3, Degree specialisation: Catalan Language & Literature].
